

Main indicators for on-farm assessment of pullet welfare

Introduction

Conditions during the rearing period can impact not only pullet welfare but can have long lasting implications affecting the subsequent laying period. For instance, foraging and injurious pecking behaviour, sensitivity to stressors, and the ability to navigate the environment have been shown to be impacted by rearing conditions (Janczak and Riber, 2015).

Animal-based, resource-based, and management-based indicators can be used to assess pullet welfare on farm. This factsheet will focus on **animal-based indicators** derived from the 2023 EFSA report on the welfare of laying hens on farm in which six highly relevant welfare consequences for pullets were identified:

1. Group stress
2. Inability to perform comfort behaviour
3. Inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour
4. Predation stress
5. Resting problems
6. Restriction of movement

Indicators that are associated with several welfare consequences (termed “iceberg indicators”) can be used to obtain a quick overview on possible welfare problems.

Legislation

Council Directive 1999/74/EC of 19 July 1999 lays down the minimum standards for protection of laying hens. However, it does not address pullets (i.e., before they begin producing eggs)

Aggressive interactions

Associated major welfare concern: group stress.

Definition: Aggressive interactions include pecks to the head area, threats, chases, and fights between birds.

Measurement: Observe (either live or through video) the number of aggressive interactions that occur in a given time frame. These interactions typically occur sporadically with a brief duration, so longer observation periods may be necessary. Additionally, presence of comb wounds or plumage damage on the back of the head may serve as an indirect indicator of aggressive behaviour.

Piling and smothering behaviour

Associated major welfare concern: group stress.

Definition: Dense clustering of birds (not to be confused with huddling due to cold thermal conditions). Sometimes with birds on top of one another. Risk of smothering (death by suffocation).

Measurement: Number of piles may be measured through observation. Frequent and regular observations may be required as this behaviour occurs sporadically, though it is more likely to occur during the afternoon. Often observed in corners of houses, but may also occur against walls, in central areas, or within nest boxes. The size of piles may be estimated by counting visible birds, but to obtain a more accurate count the birds may be gently dispersed to observe birds at the bottom of the pile. Any mortality as a result of smothering should be recorded as such.

Locomotor behaviours

Associated major welfare concern: restriction of movement.

Definition: Leg and/or wing assisted movement resulting in walking, running, jumping, or flying.

 Active behaviours will be limited if there is restriction of movement.

Measurement: Observe number of movement events during a given observation period. Proportion of time budget dedicated to active behaviours may also be assessed.

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Dustbathing

Associated major welfare concern: inability to perform comfort behaviour.

Definition: Sequence of movements that involve a pullet laying down and tossing loose material onto and between the feathers. Other behaviours that may occur during a dustbathing bout include side lying, scratching, bill raking, and head and body rubbing. The bout typically ends with the bird standing up and body shaking to remove the dust from the plumage.

 Inability to perform comfort behaviour decreases complete dustbathing behaviour and can increase incomplete or sham dustbathing (dustbathing in the absence of suitable litter material).

Measurement: Observation of number of dustbathing bouts directly or through video. Duration and frequency of behavioural components may be assessed. Dustbathing is most likely to occur during the afternoon.

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Wing flapping

Associated major welfare concern: inability to perform comfort behaviour.

Definition: Bilateral rapid upward and downward movement of the wings. Performed while standing still.

 Lack of or decreased occurrence of wing flapping may indicate insufficient space.

Measurement: Observe number of wing flapping events during a given time period, either live or through video observation.

Wing and leg stretching

Associated major welfare concern: inability to perform comfort behaviour.

Definition: Unilateral backward and downward stretch of wing and leg together.

 Lack of or decreased occurrence of wing and leg stretching may indicate lack of sufficient space to perform the behaviour. Attempted wing and leg stretching (without full wing/leg extension) may also be an indicator of insufficient space.

Measurement: Observe the number of wing and leg stretching events during a given time period, either directly or through video observation.

Walking, scratching, and pecking

Associated major welfare concern: inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour.

Definition: Walking and scratching the ground with one or two legs to expose particles and then pecking at them. Pecking may also be expressed independently of walking and scratching.

 Low ability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour or the lack of available materials may result in less walking, scratching, and pecking behaviour.

Measurement: Observe time spent or numbers of animals walking, scratching, and/or pecking.

Preening

Associated major welfare concern: inability to perform comfort behaviour.

Definition: Using the beak the feathers are lifted, cleaned, and realigned. May be performed while sitting, standing, or perching.

 Longer duration of preening indicates relaxed comfort behaviour. Short, intense bouts, particularly at night may indicate ectoparasites, feather damage, or frustration.

Measurement: Number of preening events in a given timeframe may be observed either live or through video observation. With video, more detailed data may be collected such as number of birds preening or the duration of preening bouts. Preening occurs sporadically and thus requires time for observation.

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Panting or huddling

Associated welfare concerns: poor thermal comfort.

Definition: Panting involves birds breathing through an open beak to cool themselves through evaporative cooling. Wings may also be held away from the body. On the contrary, birds may cluster close to one another (huddle) to conserve heat in cold thermal conditions.

 High occurrences of panting may be associated with heat stress, but may also be seen in stressed animals without any thermal discomfort. High occurrences of huddling may be associated with cold stress.

Measurement: Observe proportion of birds performing panting or huddling behaviour.

Reluctance to use range

Associated major welfare concern: predation stress.

Definition: Pullets will avoid the use of the outdoor range if they perceive it to be unsafe.

 Low or decreasing proportion of hens on the range could indicate a greater reluctance to use the range due to the perceived or real threat of predation.

Measurement: Estimate the percentage of the flock that is outside on the range. Note: Design of the range (e.g., size and amount/quality of cover) and time of day may impact the number of pullets going outside.

Balance problems

Associated major welfare concern: resting problems.

Definition: Signs of a loss of balance while on an elevated structure include a bird's body tilting while the tail feathers are spread and rapidly moved up and downwards. The bird's neck may be reached out. Wings may flap once or repeatedly. The hen may leave the resting sight without focusing on a landing point.

 Many observations of balance behaviours may indicate inadequate resting sites, such as slippery surfaces.

Measurement: Observation by video is recommended as this behaviour occurs sporadically and for brief duration.

Resting birds on elevated structures

Associated major welfare concern: resting problems.

Definition: Resting may occur in a standing or sitting position. The head may be forward and moving with a withdrawn neck and still body. The eyes may be closed or slowly opened and closed. Alternatively, the head may be tucked backwards into the feathers above the wing base or behind a wing.

 Birds not resting at night could indicate a lack of appropriate resting sites or inadequate resting sites.

Measurement: It is recommended to observe birds at night when nearly all birds will rest. The proportion of resting birds on elevated structures can be counted by walking in front (e.g., cages) or through (e.g., tiered systems) the enclosures. Video recordings may also be used.

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Reduced bone quality

Associated major welfare concern: restriction of movement.

Definition: Aspects of bone composition and structure that contribute to bone mineral density.

 Poor bone quality may indicate lack of opportunity for exercise.

Measurement: It can only be assessed post-mortem, either at slaughter or before depopulation on a sample of dead animals. The most common measures of bone quality include breaking force, bone ash, fat-free dry matter, bone volume and density, and bone elasticity. Note: If measured at slaughter it's important to be aware that catching and transport can contribute to bone fractures.

Iceberg indicators for on-farm assessment of pullet welfare

Fear response

Associated major welfare concerns: group stress, predation stress.

Definition: Behavioural and/or physiological reaction of animals towards sudden, threatening, and/or novel stimuli.

Measurement: There are multiple tests available to assess fear response including the tonic immobility test (e.g., Jones, 1989), novel arena test (Welfare Quality, 2009), novel object test, human approach test, the emergence test (Forkman et al., 2007) or the avoidance distance test (Whay et al., 2007; Guinebretière et al., 2020). Often a combination of tests are used. Increased fearfulness response results in longer tonic immobility durations, longer time to first sound/escape attempt, longer time to approach a novel object, and attempts to rapidly move away from the test stimulus.

Injurious pecking

Associated major welfare concerns: group stress, inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour.

Definition: Damaging pecking from one bird to another. Results in plumage damage, skin wounds, or tissue damage.

 Injurious pecking increased with the inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour – as a redirected behaviour, and with group stress.

Measurement: Observe number of injurious pecking events per individual per time unit. May be done live or through video observations. Injurious pecking is short lasting and sporadic and thus takes time to observe.

Physiological stress indicators

Associated major welfare concerns: group stress, predation stress.

Definition: Physiological changes during and after exposure to acute, intermittent, or chronic stressful conditions.

Measurement: Measures may be taken from blood, faeces, or feathers. Common measures include blood heterophil:lymphocyte ratio, corticosterone levels, catecholamine levels (e.g., epinephrine and norepinephrine). Poor body condition is also a validated measure of cumulative chronic stress. Heart rate using wearable monitors or blood pressure cuffs can be used for small-scale assessments.

Plumage condition

Associated major welfare concerns: group stress, inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour.

Definition: Deterioration or loss of plumage due to action of other birds or from abrasion from elements in the enclosure.

Measurement: Many plumage scoring systems exist to assess plumage damage. Those that require handling of birds are not recommended for use in large flocks due to the risk of stress and the fact that they are not time efficient. Instead, visual assessment of unhandled birds should be used such as the transect method. In pullets, plumage condition is generally good and severe damage (e.g., bald spots) is rare. However, visual presence of downy feathers (which appear as white spots on brown birds) may indicate mild plumage damage as outer feathers are worn away, exposing the feathers underneath. For assessment of severe damage, refer to the EURCAW-Poultry-SFA factsheet on severe feather pecking for laying hens: <https://zenodo.org/record/7373072#.ZHbyRXZByUk>

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Mortality

Associated welfare concerns: disease, group stress, predation stress, inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour.

Definition: Animals that have died, including those culled.

Measurement: Review producer's daily log of mortality including reasons listed. Pay particular attention to mortality within the first few weeks and check for deviation from the expected mortality rate based on the genotype throughout the rest of the rearing period.

Additional indicators for on-farm assessment of pullet welfare

Uniformity of body weight

Associated welfare concerns: inappropriate feeding, disease.

Definition: Uneven weight development or illness can lead to non-uniform body weights across a flock.

 Many pullets with live weights far from the mean weight may indicate inappropriate feeding (e.g., competition at the feeders) or illness.

Measurement: Monitor weight evolution and flock uniformity. Flock uniformity may be assessed by calculating the coefficient of variation (standard deviation/average flock body weight * 100)

Signs of predation

Associated major welfare concern: predation stress.

Definition: Signs of predation may include:

- animal remains characteristic of predation: carcasses with isolated puncture wounds, torn/cut feathers, broken bones with paired bite marks;
- carcasses surrounded by predator hair, feathers, droppings, or wounded animals;
- birds missing in excess of recorded mortality (e.g., culls or birds found deceased in the house).

Measurement: Inspect outdoor range area for carcasses or partial carcasses of birds. Greater numbers of remains are associated with increased predation and stress. Calculated as number of birds initially placed minus the number of birds at the end of the rearing period. Unaccounted hens can be assumed to have been lost due to predation.

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Foot lesions

Associated welfare concerns: resting problems, restriction of movement.

Definition: Lesions on the foot pad or toes.

 High prevalence of footpad lesions can be associated with poor litter quality (high moisture) or inadequate perches or flooring. Toe lesions may indicate cannibalistic behaviour.

Measurement: Observe presence and severity of footpad lesions. Lesions may range from slight discoloration and thickening of the skin up to severe injury with wounds or scabs with signs of bleeding or swelling.

Play behaviour

Associated welfare concerns: social stress, restriction of movement.

Definition: Play behaviours may include frolicking, sparring, and worm running. Frolicking involves spontaneous running with raised or flapping wings. Sparring (i.e., play fighting) involves similar elements to fighting such as jumping and making physical contact, but without aggressive pecking and injuries. Worm running involves a bird picking up a food item or other object and running with it, encouraging other birds to chase.

 Lack of play behaviour may indicate stress or restriction of movement.

Measurement: Observe occurrence of play behaviours.

Respiratory problems

Associated welfare concerns: poor air quality, disease.

Definition: Signs of respiratory illness may include coughing, sneezing, rales, gasping, discharge from the eyes or nose, swelling of the face, and/or bluish-purple discoloration of the face or wattles.

Measurement: Visually inspect birds and listen for signs of respiratory problems.

Iceberg indicators for on-farm assessment of pullet welfare

Keel bone damage

Associated welfare concerns: resting problems, restriction of movement.

Definition: Fractures, deviations, or calluses on the keel bone.

Measurement: Keel bone damage may be assessed through palpation, computed tomography, ultrasound, radiography, or automated 3D camera systems. Post-mortem assessment is considered the most accurate and feasible for large-scale assessment. Visual assessment may be performed on samples of live birds, however this method is unable to detect minor fractures or damage to the caudal fractures on the inside of the keel bone.

Pushing and jostling behaviours

Associated major welfare concerns: resting problems, restriction of movement.

Definition: When a bird makes physical contact with another, causing the latter to change its original position.

 Increased occurrence of jostling and pushing behaviours are associated with restriction of movement and resting problems.

Measurement: Observe number of pushing or jostling events in a given time period. May be done directly or through video observation. These events occur sporadically and with a brief duration and thus may take time to observe.

References

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